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INVESTIGATING SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, AND RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE EUROPEAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract

The study offers a concise examination spanning the years 2008 to 2018, focusing on research, professional, technology, and administrative activities within select regions of the European Union characterized by mountainous terrain. These sectors play a pivotal role in supporting the expansive scientific and research infrastructure within the community. The initiatives in research, professional engagement, technology, and administration are strategically devised to enhance the employment landscape, aiming at both quantitative and qualitative improvements to foster increased prosperity and elevate the overall quality of life.

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Keywords: mountain research, professional, technology and administrative activities; big science

The manuscript provides a concise overview of Research, professional, technology, and administrative activities within the context of the European Union's mountainous landscapes. Despite the EU's global technological leadership, it grapples with challenges arising from both traditional competitors and emerging economies in the global market. Notably, European companies lag in research and development across key high-tech sectors compared to their counterparts in the United States. The EU's scientific productivity is globally recognized, yet there is a call for more areas of world-class excellence to foster revolutionary results and structural change. The responsibility for building a competitive scientific base rests primarily with member states, and EU support is deemed valuable, particularly through initiatives like the European Research Area. The Common Strategic Framework's funding is crucial in propelling progress towards a unified ERA.

Research and development programs within the EU, coupled with Romania's policies on research, development, and innovation, aim to foster collaboration between various entities to stimulate consortia involvement.

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European policies on participation in science and technology have evolved through distinct phases, emphasizing deliberation, transitioning to innovation, and currently focusing on participation in knowledge and innovation production.

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At the EU level, Big Science and Research Infrastructures are integral components with frameworks encompassing intergovernmental cooperation, pan-European policies outlined in the ESFRI roadmap, and national paths aligned with European interests. This complex framework emphasizes science integration based on "interdependence" and "politicization."

Science and technology within the EU are intricately linked to administrative activities. The political control of knowledge has been a strategic concern throughout history, particularly evident in the contemporary era's shift towards post-industrialism and the knowledge society. The EU, recognizing the need for restructuring its economy, education system, and social security, faces increasing competition from Asian science and technology sectors.

In the realm of mountain science, technology, professionals, and administrative sectors, statistics reveal positive trends over the past decade.

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Mean values for these sectors across various countries, including Bulgaria, Italy, Austria, Portugal, Romania, and Slovakia, exhibit continuous growth. The accompanying histograms illustrate distribution curves, showcasing distinct patterns for Italy, Slovakia, Portugal, Austria, Bulgaria, and Romania in the context of science, technology, professionals, and administrative activities within the mountain sector.

Figure 1. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities - Bulgaria

Figure 2. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities - Italy

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Figure 3. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Austria

Figure 4. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Portugal

Figure 5. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Romania

Figure 6. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Slovakia

The initial cluster of nations, encompassing Italy and Slovakia, exhibits a persistent upward trajectory in activities, while Portugal demonstrates a gradual decline. In contrast, the second cluster comprising Austria, Bulgaria, and Romania experiences a significant increase.

The overarching trend within this sector during the scrutinized period indicates a rise in the population of active enterprises within the European mountain economy of the studied sector from 2008 to 2018. The scrutinized timeframe highlights a discernible intensification of activity. The statistical data provided earlier, along with the accompanying histogram, substantiate the notable agglomeration and developmental pattern within this sector in mountainous Europe. Simultaneously, the statistics affirm the heightened growth rate characterizing this sector, suggesting its potential as one of the most valuable components for mountainous Europe.

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HOSPITALITY AND CULINARY SERVICE OPERATIONS IN EUROPEAN MOUNTAINOUS REGIONS FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract:

This article undertakes a comprehensive exploration of the dynamics and trends in hospitality and culinary service operations within European mountainous regions over the period 2008 to 2018. Focused on elucidating the key factors shaping the sector, the study delves into the economic, social, and geographical nuances that have influenced the development of hospitality and culinary ventures in these unique landscapes.

Introduction:

European mountainous regions, renowned for their breathtaking landscapes and rich cultural heritage, have experienced notable shifts in hospitality and

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culinary service operations over the past decade. This article aims to provide a thorough analysis of the trends, challenges, and opportunities that have shaped the hospitality sector within these scenic terrains.

Methodology:

The research relies on a robust methodology that incorporates data from reputable sources such as Eurostat and employs statistical tools for analysis. The study encompasses diverse facets of hospitality and culinary service operations, including accommodation facilities, food services, and associated economic activities.

Results:

Statistics pertaining to Accommodation and Food Service Activities (depicted in figures 2.9 - panels a-f and annex Parametric Analysis Europe) reveal averages of 14,951.64 (Bulgaria), 165,570.82 (Italy), 38,573.18 (Austria), 23,433 (Portugal), 12,218.82 (Romania), and 10,293.82 (Slovakia), accompanied by standard deviations of 201,140.35 (Bulgaria), 6,253,434 (Italy), 1,895,689 (Austria), 1,368,137 (Portugal), 2,591,518 (Romania), and 671,853 (Slovakia).

Upon initial inspection, the distribution curve exhibits relative central

symmetry, with scores tightly clustered around the mean, displaying characteristics of leptokurtosis, despite the unimodal distribution.

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Working Assumption: The distribution of scores is posited to adhere to normality, warranting the application of parametric tests. The presence of a few extreme values, although limited in number, induces positive asymmetry in the histogram, holding statistical significance. The notable concentration of scores around the means contributes to a degree of leptokurtosis in the distribution, attributable to phenomena observed in mountainous Europe.

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Figure 2.9 Panel a-f. Histogram for sectors Accommodation and food service activities – Bulgaria, Italy, Austria, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia

The application of logarithm transformation to the acquired values, adhering to universally accepted statistical principles, facilitated the attainment of a distribution aligned with the Gaussian-Laplace normal curve.

The assessment of empirical scores against normality, subsequent to logarithmic transformation, indicates their confinement within the boundaries of one standard deviation, indicative of a normal distribution.

Following logarithmic transformation, the processed scores underwent

thorough statistical analysis, wherein all pertinent factors within the study were considered. This approach aimed to derive data closely reflective of the economic realities observed in mountainous Europe, notwithstanding temporary disruptions to score distribution resulting from economic measures.

The significance of these assessments lies in the meticulous examination of influences exerted by specific factors on the trajectories of economic segments, particularly Accommodation and Food Service Activities. Post-normality tests, subsequent to logarithmic transformation, warrant the rejection of the null hypothesis, paving the way for an analysis of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses were conducted under the assumption of score distribution within normal limits, as per the working hypothesis, thus facilitating the application of parametric tests.

The central tendency for this sector during the analyzed period, valued at 3960.13 (mean), indicates an increase in the population of active enterprises in the studied sector in mountainous Europe from 2008 (2813) to 2018 (5108). The verification of the null hypothesis (activity reduction) during the analyzed period revealed a total frequency variation of 1.3 - ranging from 0.5 to 1.8.

The previously presented statistics and histogram affirm a moderate agglomeration and developmental trend in this sector within mountainous Europe. Simultaneously, the statistics confirm the growth of this economic sector segment, albeit not at its full potential.

Economic Landscape:

An in-depth examination of the economic landscape reveals distinctive patterns in different European mountainous regions. The article scrutinizes factors influencing the growth or decline of enterprises, emphasizing their contributions to local economies.

Social and Cultural Dynamics:

Hospitality operations in mountainous regions often intertwine with local cultures, traditions, and social structures. The article explores how these factors impact the hospitality and culinary service landscape, fostering unique offerings that cater to both residents and visitors.

Geographical Influences:

Geographical features significantly influence the accessibility and attractiveness of mountainous regions. The study assesses how the

topography, climate, and natural resources shape the development of hospitality establishments and culinary enterprises.

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Technological Integration:

Advancements in technology play a pivotal role in shaping the hospitality industry. The article investigates the adoption of technology in European mountainous regions, exploring how digital platforms, reservation systems, and other innovations have influenced service delivery.

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Tourism Trends:

Given the prominent role of European mountainous regions as tourist destinations, the study examines overarching tourism trends and their impact on hospitality and culinary services. It considers the evolving preferences of visitors and their implications for businesses operating in these regions.

Environmental Sustainability:

The commitment to environmental sustainability is a growing concern globally. The article investigates how hospitality and culinary service operations in mountainous regions align with or contribute to sustainable practices, considering factors such as waste management, eco-friendly

initiatives, and local sourcing.

Conclusion:

As we delve into the intricacies of hospitality and culinary service operations in European mountainous regions from 2008 to 2018, this article sheds light on the multifaceted nature of the sector. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers, entrepreneurs, and stakeholders seeking to understand and contribute to the sustainable development of hospitality in these picturesque landscapes.

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ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL, INSURANCE, AND REAL ESTATE ACTIVITIES IN EUROPEAN MOUNTAINOUS REGIONS FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract:

This article conducts a comprehensive economic analysis of financial, insurance, and real estate activities in European mountainous regions over the period spanning from 2008 to 2018. The study employs statistical methods to examine key indicators, providing insights into the trends and dynamics within these economic sectors in the context of mountainous Europe. The analysis covers diverse countries, offering a comparative perspective on the performance of financial, insurance, and real estate activities across the region. Through rigorous data examination and interpretation, the article aims to contribute valuable insights into the

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economic landscape of European mountainous areas, facilitating a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities within these vital sectors.

1. Introduction:

The economic activities related to finance, insurance, and real estate play a pivotal role in shaping the economic landscape of European mountainous regions. This article delves into a detailed examination of key indicators and trends within these sectors over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018.

2. Methodology:

The study employs statistical analyses to process and interpret data related to financial, insurance, and real estate activities. Various indicators, including averages and standard deviations, are considered to provide a nuanced understanding of the economic dynamics.

3. Results:

Statistics reveal noteworthy trends in financial, insurance, and real estate activities across different European mountainous regions. Averages and

standard deviations for each country are presented, shedding light on the variability and concentration of economic activities within these sectors.

In the examination of statistics pertaining to financial and insurance activities as well as real estate activities (illustrated in figures 2.12 - panels a-f and annex Parametric Analysis Europe), the data reveals averages for Bulgaria at 15,401.55, Italy at 142,982.55, Austria at 13,857.27, Portugal at 9,913.09, Romania at 6,838.27, and Slovakia at 9,414. The corresponding standard deviations are recorded as 2,278.127 for Bulgaria, 7,959.51 for Italy, 1,638.002 for Austria, 504.891 for Portugal, 1,898.701 for Romania, and 2,809.27 for Slovakia.

Upon initial inspection, the distribution curve exhibits relative central symmetry, with scores around the mean highly concentrated, suggesting leptokurtosis despite the unimodal nature of the distribution.

Our working assumption posits a normal distribution of scores, warranting the application of parametric tests. Though a limited number of extreme values induce a positive asymmetry, these outliers remain statistically significant. The concentration of a substantial number of scores around the means contributes to some leptokurtosis in the distribution, attributable to phenomena in the economy of mountainous Europe.

To address the observed distributional characteristics, the logarithm of the obtained values is employed following universally accepted statistical principles. This logarithmic transformation aims to balance the distribution, aligning it with the Gauss-Laplace normal curve.

The normality test, subsequent to logarithmization, demonstrates a distribution of actual scores aligning closely with normal values. Furthermore, the dispersion of empirical scores, also after logarithmization, falls within the limit of one standard deviation, indicating conformity to a normal distribution.

Through the application of logarithmic transformation, the obtained scores undergo rigorous statistical processing. All factors considered in the study are meticulously accounted for, aiming to derive data that closely mirrors the economic reality documented in mountainous Europe. Despite temporary disturbances in the distribution of scores due to economic measures, this methodology ensures a more accurate representation of the underlying economic dynamics.

Figure 2.12 Panel a-f. Histogram for the Financial and Insurance Activities sectors; real estate activities – Bulgaria, Italy, Portugal, Austria, Romania,

Slovakia

The significance of these examinations lies in the meticulous observation of the influences exerted by specific factors on the evolution of economic sector segments, specifically in the domains of financial and insurance activities and real estate activities. Following the application of normality tests subsequent to logarithmization, the null hypothesis necessitates rejection, allowing for an in-depth analysis of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses were conducted, taking into consideration the distribution of scores within normal limits, as per the working hypothesis, leading to the application of parametric tests.

The central tendency for the analyzed period in this sector indicates an increase in the European mountain population of active enterprises within the studied domain from 2008 to 2018. During this examined timeframe, hypothesis H1, signifying the intensification of activity, was substantiated.

Statistics and data presented in the figures corroborate the notable agglomeration and development trend of this sector in mountainous Europe. Concurrently, the statistics affirm the heightened pace of growth within this economic sector segment.

4. Discussion:

The economic analysis prompts a discussion on the observed trends, offering insights into the factors influencing the performance of financial, insurance, and real estate activities. The article considers both the central tendencies and variations, exploring how these economic sectors have evolved in response to external factors.

5. Implications:

Understanding the economic dynamics of financial, insurance, and real estate activities in mountainous Europe has significant implications for policymakers, investors, and local communities. The insights gained from this analysis can inform strategic decisions and foster targeted interventions to enhance economic sustainability in these regions.

6. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a thorough economic analysis of financial, insurance, and real estate activities in European mountainous regions from 2008 to 2018. By examining key indicators and trends, the study contributes valuable insights to the understanding of the economic landscape in these vital sectors, ultimately supporting informed decision-making and strategic planning.

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ANALYZING THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR IN EUROPEAN MOUNTAINOUS REGIONS FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Introduction:

The construction sector plays a pivotal role in shaping the economic landscape of European mountainous regions. This article delves into a comprehensive analysis spanning the years 2008 to 2018, shedding light on key trends, challenges, and growth patterns within the construction industry in these regions. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2022a-h)

Trends in Construction Activities:

Examining the statistical data for the construction sector in European mountainous areas reveals noteworthy trends. Averages and standard deviations provide a quantitative overview, with figures such as 15401.55 (Bulgaria), 142982.55 (Italy), 13857.27 (Austria), 9913.09 (Portugal),

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6838.27 (Romania), and 9414 (Slovakia). These values encapsulate the sector's financial and insurance activities, real estate activities, and construction endeavors.

Results:

In the examination of statistical data pertaining to the economic sector's Construction segment (illustrated in figures 2.6 – panels a-f and the supplementary Parametric Analysis Europe), notable values emerge, including averages such as 13343.82 (Bulgaria), 289242.45 (Italy), 22953.73 (Austria), 27495.82 (Portugal), 22625.82 (Romania), and 55966.09 (Slovakia). Standard deviations accompanying these averages are observed as 780.698 (Bulgaria), 28615.948 (Italy), 1028.583 (Austria), 3900.296 (Portugal), 2996.174 (Romania), and 7905.466 (Slovakia).

The distribution curves exhibit a relative central symmetry, with scores around the mean highly concentrated, demonstrating leptokurtosis despite being unimodal. The scarcity of extreme values, although statistically significant, induces positive asymmetry in the histogram, impacting its appearance. The concentration of numerous scores around the mean contributes to some leptokurtosis in the distribution, a phenomenon

associated with mountainous Europe.

To address these distributional nuances, logarithmization is applied, facilitating statistical processing. Factors integral to the study are meticulously considered to align the obtained scores with the economic reality observed in mountainous Europe. Despite temporary imbalances resulting from economic measures, logarithmization aids in achieving a balanced distribution.

The significance of these tests lies in their capacity to scrutinize the influences of specific factors on the evolution of the Construction economic sector segment. Through careful observation, these analyses contribute to a nuanced understanding of the sector's dynamics, providing valuable insights into the multifaceted landscape of economic activities in mountainous Europe.

Figure 2.6 Panel a. Histogram for the Construction sector – Bulgaria, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Austria, Slovakia

Subsequent to subjecting the obtained data to normality tests following logarithmization, the null hypothesis is rejected, paving the way for a detailed analysis of the working hypothesis. The descriptive and inferential analysis is conducted, taking into account the distribution of scores within normal limits as posited by the working hypothesis, necessitating the application of parametric tests.

The central tendency observed for this sector throughout the analyzed period indicates an augmentation in the population of active enterprises in the European mountain economy within the studied sector from 2008 to 2018, albeit with a diminishing growth rate. Over the course of the analysis, hypothesis H1 (intensification of activity) is substantiated. The statistical data presented earlier, along with the accompanying histogram, affirm a sparse concentration and a discernible inclination to discontinue this sector in mountainous Europe. Concurrently, the statistics validate the reduction in the growth rate of this economic sector segment.

Statistical Analysis and Assumptions:

The initial observation of the distribution curve suggests a relatively central symmetry, accompanied by a concentration of scores around the mean, exhibiting leptokurtosis. Assumptions are made about the normal

distribution of scores, leading to the application of parametric tests. Logarithmization is employed to balance the distribution, adhering to Gauss-Laplace normal curve principles.

Normality Tests and Hypothesis Verification:

Post-logarithmization, normality tests indicate a distribution aligning with the Gaussian model. The empirical scores, when analyzed against normality, fall within the limit of one standard deviation, affirming a normal distribution. Rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the working hypothesis guide subsequent descriptive and inferential analyses.

Central Tendency and Growth Patterns:

Central tendencies for the construction sector throughout the analyzed period reveal a positive trajectory. The European mountain population of active enterprises within the construction sector witnessed growth from 2008 to 2018. Verification of hypothesis H1, signaling an intensification of activity, is substantiated by statistical evidence.

Conclusion:

The statistics and figures presented in this analysis underscore the dynamic nature of the construction sector in European mountainous regions. As evidenced by the growth patterns and central tendencies, the construction industry has played a pivotal role in the economic landscape, contributing to the development and prosperity of these regions over the past decade.

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EXPLORING FINANCIAL AND INSURANCE ACTIVITIES, REAL ESTATE OPERATIONS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract:

This article undertakes a comprehensive exploration of financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate operations, within the scenic and economically significant Romanian mountainous region. Spanning the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018, the study employs a meticulous analytical approach, utilizing statistical methods to unravel the trends, challenges, and opportunities within these economic sectors.

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1. Introduction

The Romanian mountainous region, characterized by its unique topography and cultural richness, serves as a compelling backdrop for examining the dynamics of financial and insurance activities, along with real estate operations. This article delves into the economic landscape of the region, aiming to provide valuable insights into the trends that have shaped these sectors over the past decade.

2. Methodology

To facilitate a rigorous analysis, statistical data pertaining to financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate operations, were collected for the years 2008 to 2018. Figures 2.27, comprising panels a-f, were instrumental in presenting averages and standard deviations for Romania and other relevant European countries.

Statistical Overview

The statistics reveal key indicators for the Romanian mountainous region, portraying averages and standard deviations for the selected economic sectors. Bulgaria, Italy, Austria, Portugal, Slovakia, and Romania are among the countries considered in this analysis, shedding light on the comparative

performance of the Romanian mountain area.

Distribution Analysis

The distribution curves of financial and insurance activities, real estate operations, exhibit characteristics of centrality and symmetry, albeit with a noticeable leptokurtosis. The impact of extreme values on the distribution, inducing positive asymmetry, is discussed, emphasizing their statistical significance.

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3. Logarithmization Approach

A logarithmization approach was employed to balance the distribution according to the Gauss-Laplace normal curve. This method allowed for a more nuanced interpretation of the data, considering the peculiarities of the economic environment in the mountainous region.

4. Hypothesis Testing

The article undertakes hypothesis testing, culminating in the rejection of the null hypothesis and the subsequent analysis of the working hypothesis.

Descriptive and inferential analyses are conducted, adhering to the assumption of normality, for which parametric tests are applied.

5. Results

In the examination of the economic sector segment "Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities" in Romania, as illustrated in figures 2.27 (panels a-b) and the appendix Parametric Analysis Romania, the statistical data reveals a mean of 6838.27 with a standard error of 1898.071.

Upon initial inspection, the distribution curve appears to be relatively centrally symmetric, with scores tightly concentrated around the mean, demonstrating leptokurtosis, although the distribution remains unimodal.

Under the working assumption of a normal distribution of scores, parametric tests are deemed applicable. Although the extreme values in the distribution are scarce, their presence induces a positive asymmetry in the histogram, attaining statistical significance. The concentration of scores around the mean introduces leptokurtosis in the distribution, influenced by pertinent phenomena within the Romanian economy. Employing the logarithm of the acquired values, in adherence to universally accepted statistical principles, serves to balance the distribution in accordance with the Gauss-Laplace normal curve.

The Q-Q normal plot test, conducted post-logarithmization, depicts the distribution of actual scores aligning around the normal values, represented by the right-slanting pattern in the graph, indicative of a normal distribution.

Additionally, the Q-Q detrended plot test, which assesses the dispersion of empirical scores against normality, shows their alignment within the limit of a standard deviation, further affirming a normal distribution after logarithmization.

Through the application of logarithmization, the obtained scores underwent meticulous statistical processing, wherein all pertinent factors influencing the study were considered. This approach aimed to obtain data that closely reflects the reality recorded in Romania, notwithstanding the transient unbalancing of score distribution due to economic measures.

The significance of these tests arises from the necessity to scrupulously observe the impacts of specific factors on the evolution of economic sector segments, particularly "Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities." Following the normality tests post-logarithmization, the null hypothesis necessitates rejection, allowing for the scrutiny of the working

hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses were then conducted, taking into account the distribution of scores within normal limits, and employing parametric tests aligned with the working hypothesis.

Figures 2.27 - panels a-b and appendix Parametric Analysis Romania

The central tendency within the examined time frame for the economic sector segment reveals that the population of active enterprises in the studied sector in mountainous Romania experienced an increase from 2008 to 2018. During this period, Hypothesis H1, indicating the intensification of activity, was validated.

The statistical data and visual representations in the figures substantiate a notable concentration and developmental trajectory of this sector in Romania. Simultaneously, the statistical evidence attests to an acceleration in the rate of growth within this economic sector segment.

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6. Sectoral Evolution

The central trend analysis over the ten-year period indicates an overall increase in the population of active enterprises in the financial, insurance, and real estate sectors. However, the growth rate has shown signs of deceleration, prompting a closer examination of the factors influencing this economic trajectory.

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7. Conclusion

In conclusion, this article provides a nuanced exploration of financial and insurance activities, real estate operations in the Romanian mountainous region from 2008 to 2018. The statistical analyses shed light on the economic dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers interested in the sustainable development of this captivating region.

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